

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

January 15, 2026
UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

January 15, 2026
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International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

Chiziqsiz chegaraviy shartlar bilan bog'langan issiqlik tarqalish tenglamalar sistemasining yechimlari xossalari

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Ushbu maqolada

$$Q_+ = (x, t) : x \in R_+^N, 0 < t < +\infty$$

sohada aniqlangan ko'p komponentli muhitlarda nochizikli chegaraviy shartlar bilan bog'langan quyidagi:

$$\begin{cases} u_{it} = \nabla(|\nabla u_i|^{m_i-1} \nabla u_i), & x \in R_+^N, t > 0 \\ -|\nabla u_i|^{m_i-1} \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_1} = u_{i+1}^{q_i}, & u_{k+1} = u_1, x_1 = 0, t > 0 \\ u(x, 0) = u_0(x), & x \in R_+^N, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

issiqlik tarqalish masalasini qaraymiz. Bu yerda $m_i > 0, q_i > 0$ $u_0(x)$ - uzluksiz, manfiy bo'lmagan, chegaralangan funksiyadir. U quyidagi shartlarini qanoatlantiradi,

$$-|\nabla u_{i0}|^{m_i-1} \frac{\partial u_{i0}}{\partial x_1} = u_{(i+1)0}^{q_i}, \quad x_1 = 0$$

va ba'zi $x \in R_+^N$ nuqta uchun $\sup p u_0 \subset B_R(x_0) \cap R_+^N$, $u_0 \neq 0$ bo'ladi. Shu bilan birga, boshlang'ich qiymat $u_0(x)$ kichik soha tashqarisida nolga teng bo'lsa ham, yechimlar chekli vaqt ichida blow-up holatga kelishi mumkin. (1) tenglamani o'ziga xos xususiyati shundaki, unda diffuziya koeffitsiyenti gradientga bog'liqdir. Bunday turdagi tenglamalar gradientga bog'liq issiqlik tarqalish jarayonlarini ifodalaydi. Ma'lumki, (1) tenglamalar sistemasi buziluvchi bo'lib, $u_i(x, t) = 0$ yoki $|\nabla u_i| = 0$ bo'lganda klassik ma'noda yechimga ega bo'lmasligi mumkin. Shuning uchun (1) masalaning $|\nabla u_i|^{m_i-1} \nabla u_i \in C(R_+^N \times (0, +\infty))$, $0 < u_i \in C(Q)$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, k$) sinfda umumlashgan yechimi qaraladi va bu yechim (1) tenglamalar sistemasini integral ayniyat ma'nosida yoki taqsimot ma'nosida qanoatlantiradi.

[1-8] ishlarda nochizikli chegaraviy shartlarga ega kvazichizikli, chiziqsiz tenglamalar va ularning sistemalari o'rganilgan. Xususan, [9] ishda Huang, Yin va Wang tomonidan [4] adabiyotdagi masalani ko'p o'lchovli holatga kengaytirganlar:

$$\begin{cases} u_t = \Delta u^m & x \in R_+^N, 0 < t < T \\ -\frac{\partial u^m}{\partial x_1} u^p(x, t), & x_1 = 0, 0 < t < T \\ u(x, 0) = u_0(x), & x \in R_+^N, \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Ular yuqoridagi masala uchun kritik ko'rsatkichlar $p_0 = \frac{1}{2}(m+1)$ va $p_c = m + \frac{1}{N}$

ekanligini aniqlaganlar. Biroq, [4] adabiyotdagi masalaning ko'p o'lchovli holatidagi kritik ko'rsatkichlari hali noma'lum bo'lgan.

[10] adabiyotda quyidagi tez diffuziyali Nyuton tipiga kirmaydigan tenglamalar uchun kritik ko'rsatkichlarni aniqlashgan, global yechim va chegaralanmagan yechimning hosil bo'lish shartlarini topishgan

$$u_{it} = (|u_{ix}|^{m_i-1}u_{ix})_x, (i = 1, 2, \dots, k), (x, t) \in R_+ \times (0, +\infty) \quad (3)$$

tenglamalar noxizizli chegaraviy shart orqali o'zaro bog'langan:

$$-|u_{ix}|^{m_i-1}u_{ix}(0, t) = u_{i+1}^{p_i}(0, t), (i = 1, 2, \dots, k), u_{k+1} := u_1, t \in (0, +\infty) \quad (4)$$

$$u_i(x, 0) = u_{i0}(x), (i = 1, 2, \dots, k), x \in R_+ \quad (5)$$

Boshlang'ich shartlar nolga teng bo'lmagan, nomanfiy, cheklangan va yetarlicha silliq. Bu yerda $0 < m_i < 1, p_i > 0$. (3) tenglamalar tez diffuziya turiga mansub bo'lgani sababli, (3)_B (5) sistemaning yechimi har qanday $t > 0$ da butun fazoda musbat qiymat qabul qiladi. Ular tez diffuziya xususiyatiga ega bo'lgan Nyuton tipidagi sistema uchun qo'yilgan noxizizli chegaraviy masalaning kritik ko'rsatkichini ko'rib chiqdilar. Yuqori va quyi avtomodel yechimlarni qurish yordamida yechimning global mavjudlik va Fujita tipidagi kritik eksponentialarni topishgan.

Ta'rif [11]: $u_i(x, t)$ funksiya Q sohada (1) masalaning yuqori (quyi) yechimi deyiladi, agar $u_i(x, t) = 0$ da $Q/D_i, D_t = x < l(t) \times (0, +\infty), u_{i1}(x, t) \in C_{t,x}^{1,2}(D_t) \cap C(Q), -|\nabla u_i|^{m_i-1} \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_1} \in C(Q)$ va quyidagi shartlarni qanoatlantirsa: $u_{it} \geq (\leq) \nabla(|\nabla u_i|^{m_i-1} \nabla u_i), -|\nabla u_i|^{m_i-1} \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_i} \geq (\leq) u_{i+1}^{q_i}, u(x, 0) \geq (\leq) u_0(x), x \in R$

Natijalar va muhokama

Teorema1. Agar $\min N\beta_i - \alpha_i$ shart bajarilsa, u holda (1) masalaning yechimi global bo'ladi.

Isbot: (1) teoremaning isboti yechimlarni taqqoslash usuliga asoslanadi. Buning uchun $Q_+ = (x, t) : x \in R_+^N, 0 < t < +\infty$ sohada quyidagi ko'rinishdagi taqqoslanadigan yechim quramiz.

$$\bar{u}_{i+}(x, t) = (\tau + t)^{-\alpha_i} g_i(\eta_i) \quad (6)$$

$$\text{bu yerda } \eta_i = x(\tau + t)^{\beta_i}, \alpha_i = \frac{-\alpha_1 q_i(1 + m_i) - m_i}{2m_i}, \beta_i = \frac{m_i - \alpha_1 q_i(1 - m_i)}{2m_i}$$

Shunday bo'lishi uchun $\bar{u}_+(x, t)$ (1) masalaning yuqori yechimi bo'lsin, $g_i(\eta_i)$ funksiyasi quyidagi tengsizlikni qanoatlantirishi kerak:

$$\frac{dg_i}{d\eta_i} = -b_i \frac{1 + m_i}{m_i - 1} \left(a_i - b_i \eta_i^{\frac{1+m_i}{m_i}} \right)^{\frac{1}{m_i-1}} \frac{1}{\eta_i^{\frac{1}{m_i}}}. \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{d}{d\eta_i} \left(\eta_i^N \left(a_i - b_i \eta_i^{\frac{1+m_i}{m_i}} \right)^{\frac{m_i}{m_i-1}} \right) = \eta_i^{N-1} \left(N \left(a_i - b_i \eta_i^{\frac{1+m_i}{m_i}} \right)^{\frac{m_i}{m_i-1}} - b_i \frac{1 + m_i}{m_i - 1} \eta_i^{\frac{1}{m_i}} \left(a_i - b_i \eta_i^{\frac{1+m_i}{m_i}} \right)^{\frac{1}{m_i-1}} \right). \quad (8)$$

$$\bar{g}_i(\eta_i) = (a_i - b_i \eta_i^{\frac{1+m_i}{m_i}})^{\frac{m_i}{m_i-1}}$$

ohirgi tenglikdan (7) va (8) ni hosil qilinib, avtomodel yechimga qo'yish orqali quyidagilarni hosil qilamiz.

$$\begin{aligned} & \eta_i^{1-N} \frac{d}{d\eta_i} \left[\eta_i^{N-1} \left(-b_i \frac{1+m_i}{m_i-1} \right) \eta_i \left(a_i - b_i \eta_i^{\frac{1+m_i}{m_i}} \right)^{\frac{m_i}{m_i-1}} \right] + \\ & + \alpha_i g_i(\eta_i) + \eta_i \beta_i \left(-b_i \frac{1+m_i}{m_i-1} \right) \left(a_i - b_i \eta_i^{\frac{1+m_i}{m_i}} \right)^{\frac{1}{m_i-1}} \frac{1}{\eta_i^{\frac{1}{m_i}}} \leq 0, \\ & \eta_i^{1-N} \left(-b_i \frac{1+m_i}{m_i-1} \right) \eta_i^{N-1} \left[N \left(a_i - b_i \eta_i^{\frac{1+m_i}{m_i}} \right)^{\frac{m_i}{m_i-1}} - b_i \frac{1+m_i}{m_i-1} \eta_i^{\frac{1}{m_i}} \left(a_i - b_i \eta_i^{\frac{1+m_i}{m_i}} \right)^{\frac{1}{m_i-1}} \right] + \\ & + \alpha_i g_i(\eta_i) + \eta_i \beta_i \left(-b_i \frac{1+m_i}{m_i-1} \right) \left(a_i - b_i \eta_i^{\frac{1+m_i}{m_i}} \right)^{\frac{1}{m_i-1}} \frac{1}{\eta_i^{\frac{1}{m_i}}} \leq 0, \\ & - \beta_i N \left(a_i - b_i \eta_i^{\frac{1+m_i}{m_i}} \right)^{\frac{m_i}{m_i-1}} + \eta_i \beta_i \frac{1+m_i}{m_i-1} \left(a_i - b_i \eta_i^{\frac{1+m_i}{m_i}} \right)^{\frac{1}{m_i-1}} \frac{1}{\eta_i^{\frac{1}{m_i}}} + \\ & + \alpha_i g_i(\eta_i) - \eta_i \beta_i \frac{1+m_i}{m_i-1} \left(a_i - b_i \eta_i^{\frac{1+m_i}{m_i}} \right)^{\frac{1}{m_i-1}} \frac{1}{\eta_i^{\frac{1}{m_i}}} \leq 0, \\ & - \beta_i N g_i(\eta_i) + \alpha_i g_i(\eta_i) \leq 0, \quad g_i(\eta_i) (\alpha_i - \beta_i N) \leq 0. \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Shunday qilib, ko'rinib turibdiki $g_i(\eta_i)$ bo'lgani uchun $\min N\beta_i - \alpha_i > 0$ bo'ladi.

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